

Governance and Collaboration Framework

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Disclaimer

The COcyber project funded under Grant Agreement No. 101158606 is supported by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre and funded by the European Union.

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Introduction

The COcyber Community requires a governance and collaboration framework that enables trusted cybersecurity information sharing, joint capability development, and coordinated delivery among organisations that may operate across sectors or jurisdictions. Concretely, this framework, submitted as an Annex of D6.6 COcyber Final Sustainability Plan and as a standalone document in the Zenodo repository, should enable replicability outside the project for all those organisations that would like to take over the role of facilitator for Civilian and Defence joint activities in the cybersecurity domain. The lessons learned throughout the implementation of the project provide the foundation for a governance and collaboration framework that can be replicated beyond the lifetime of the initiative. The framework is designed to support any organisation willing to assume a facilitation role in the field of civilian-defence cybersecurity cooperation. Rather than creating a rigid governance model, the framework promotes a flexible and scalable approach that can adapt to different organisational contexts while maintaining a consistent set of principles.

One of the main items that the framework regulates is the engagement of a community of practitioners with different operational backgrounds, from highly bureaucratic organisations with many limitations, such as Ministries of Defence, to agile and fast-reacting innovators and start-ups working on cybersecurity. The COcyber project has demonstrated the value of a dedicated collaborative environment capable of connecting stakeholders from both civilian and defence domains. Through its activities, community-building efforts, and digital platform, COcyber has piloted a practical model for facilitating dual-use cybersecurity engagement at the European level. This framework ensures relevance and timely participation of both communities to foster dialogue and collaboration. Moreover, the framework provides the organisational principles, governance arrangements, stakeholder engagement mechanisms, and operational processes necessary to ensure the sustainable functioning of a dual-use cybersecurity ecosystem, making sure that all interactions, from event promotion to follow-ups, are directed to the functioning and maintenance of the COcyber platform as the main entry point in the cybersecurity dual-use field.

Therefore, the framework is designed to remain lightweight and adaptable while ensuring smooth activities/events delivery, transparent decision making and data entry security in terms of data and information sharing, and accountability – who is responsible and for what. It adopts a member-driven and secretariat run structure that balances strategic oversight with operational efficiency and community participation.

1 Purpose of the Governance Framework

The Governance and Collaboration Framework establishes the structures and responsibilities necessary to ensure sustainable cooperation between cybersecurity stakeholders operating across civilian and defence domains. Its primary purpose is to create a trusted environment where organisations can collaborate effectively while preserving their individual mandates and responsibilities. In practice, this means providing clear governance arrangements that support decision-making, stakeholder engagement, information sharing and operational coordination.

The framework pursues several strategic objectives. First, it facilitates structured knowledge exchange between different cybersecurity communities. The increasing sophistication of cyber threats requires organisations to continuously learn from each other, share best practices and develop common approaches to challenges. Second, it promotes dialogue between civilian and defence stakeholders. While both communities often face similar risks, opportunities for interaction remain limited. The framework therefore establishes dedicated mechanisms that encourage communication and cooperation. Third, it supports capability development through collaborative activities such as six different types of workshops and events: Capacity building activities, cybersecurity consultations, Digital and Cyber Dialogues, High-level Round tables, Policy-oriented workshops, and Research and Innovation seminars. These activities help participants strengthen their expertise. Fourth, the framework encourages the development of synergies between European cybersecurity initiatives. Many projects address similar challenges but operate independently. By creating links between initiatives, COcyber contributes to reducing fragmentation within the European cybersecurity landscape. Finally, the framework aims to ensure the long-term sustainability of the collaboration model by establishing governance mechanisms that remain relevant beyond the duration of a specific project.

2 Governance Structure

2.1 COcyber Secretariat

The Secretariat serves as the operational and administrative backbone of the framework. It coordinates activities, manages stakeholder engagement, supports governance processes and ensures continuity between strategic discussions and practical implementation.

To fulfil these responsibilities, the Secretariat performs five primary functions: operational coordination, community management, administrative management, and communication and dissemination. Clear documentation and transparent processes are essential to maintaining trust and ensuring that community members understand how activities are organised and how decisions are implemented.

In the COcyber project the Secretariat was composed by the three COcyber partners leading the organisation and communication for external activities: EOS (leading WP2 – coordination activities) took on the role of chair of the Secretariat, 28DIGITAL (the COcyber project coordinator) took on the role of Administrative coordinator, and AUS (leading WP5 – Dissemination and Communication) took on the role of Communications Coordinator.

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Within the secretariat, each role is crafted to ensure that the community's operations are both seamless and responsive to its evolving needs and members' feedback. The Chair of Secretariat provides overarching leadership, coordinating tasks and ensuring that all activities align with the project objectives, including the monitoring of related KPIs. The chair is also responsible for giving written approval for the organization of a COcyber activity, once the Activity proposal has been accepted by the Secretariat, to the partner organizing the event and function as primary contact for activity related exchanges, except for communication and marketing tasks.

The administrative coordinator ensures that the Community activities remain aligned with the agreed timeline, budgetary provisions and applicable regulatory requirements. This role includes providing activity organisers with the necessary tools and templates to keep appropriate records, such as participant lists, event recordings and summaries of main takeaways. It also includes supervising the procurement of venues and logistical arrangements, including catering and related services, approving the selection of paid experts by reviewing relevant documentation such as CVs and motivation statements, providing non-disclosure agreements when required, particularly for closed-door meetings involving defence stakeholders, preparing collaboration agreements with other projects or

initiatives, supporting arrangements governing data flows between project partners, and managing the contracting and payment of COcyber Ambassadors.

The Communications Coordinator is responsible for internal and external communications of the COcyber Community. They ensure that outgoing messages are clear, timely, and consistent with the community's values and manage the customer relationship management tools such as BREVO, which is used to communicate with the community. They are also responsible for the management of the social media channels, such as LinkedIn and BlueSky, which are used to expand and inform the community of events, surveys, and other engagement opportunities.

The Secretariat provides support in the creation of COcyber activities. The chair of the secretariat, regularly invites and reminds the consortium partners to insert their envisioned events in the timeline. This preliminary stage of the event planning helps with the management and the coordination of the activities by the Secretariat, ensuring that activities are on track to reach KPIs. Then Consortium members submit, preferably a month before the date of the event, an Activity Proposal following the template based on the D4.3 Toolkit for the organisation of know-how and information-sharing activities. Within one week of the submission of the Activity Proposal, the Secretariat goes over the Proposal and provides suggestions for improvement where needed, before the chair of the Secretariat gives written approval for the organization of the activity. To streamline this process a slack channel dedicated to the Secretariat was created where the Secretariat could discuss the concept of the Activity. Then the Communication Coordinator of the Secretariat, will promote the event to the community and all target stakeholders. This event promotion includes an announcement under project's events-page, a dedicated social media post and invitation email to community members with Brevo (the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system). Following the conclusion of the event, the Secretariat helps disseminate a survey to gather feedback from the participants to the events and blog posts covering the outcomes of the event.

2.2 COcyber Community

The COcyber Community represents the broader stakeholder community and acts as the primary consultative and participatory body.

The Community brings together organisations and experts from across the European cybersecurity ecosystem, including national cybersecurity authorities, ministries of defence and defence cyber organisations, European institutions and agencies, critical infrastructure

operators, private-sector cybersecurity companies, SMEs, start-ups, research organisations and academic institutions. This diversity is one of the main strengths of the COcyber approach because it allows discussions to reflect operational realities from multiple perspectives.

Community members contribute through the COcyber activities and engagement strategies such as surveys, consultations, and interviews. They feed results such as NEEDS Assessments, PESTEL analysis, National Case Studies, Policy recommendations, and validate tools such as platforms. They provide feedback on strategic priorities, identify challenges, share expertise and help shape best practices and provide connections for future initiatives. The Community also plays an important role in validating relevance. By bringing together practitioners, policymakers, researchers and industry representatives, it helps ensure that proposed activities respond to real operational needs rather than purely theoretical considerations. This feedback loop improves the quality of events, discussions and outputs produced within the ecosystem.

The COcyber Community offers a replicable model for building and sustaining a multi-stakeholder ecosystem around civilian-defence cybersecurity cooperation. Its replication depends on recreating the core elements that made the Community effective: a diverse membership base, a clear facilitation structure, regular engagement activities and structured feedback loops. Any organisation wishing to replicate the model should first identify and mobilise relevant actors from across the cybersecurity ecosystem. This diversity is essential because it ensures that discussions reflect practical realities, institutional constraints and operational needs from different perspectives. The Community should then be engaged through a combination of surveys, consultations, interviews, workshops and platform-based activities, allowing members to contribute to project results. A key lesson from COcyber is that the Community should not be treated only as an audience, but as a consultative and participatory body that helps shape priorities, validate relevance and improve outputs. By creating regular opportunities for feedback, knowledge exchange and connection-building, the model can be replicated by other initiatives seeking to develop trusted cooperation between civilian and defence cybersecurity stakeholders and to ensure that their activities remain grounded in real stakeholder needs.

2.2.1 COcyber Ambassadors

One of the key elements of the COcyber Community are the Ambassadors. They are a dynamic network of key cybersecurity actors across EU Member States who act as

advocates for the project. The COcyber Ambassador Programme was designed around a simple but effective principle: trusted people are often the most credible entry points into specialised communities. In the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres, where trust, mandate boundaries and sensitivity of information are central concerns, engagement cannot rely only on general communication campaigns or open invitations. It requires recognised experts, policymakers, decision-makers and practitioners who can explain the value of the initiative, identify relevant stakeholders, encourage participation and create bridges between communities that do not always interact regularly. Ambassadors therefore act as intermediaries between the COcyber Community and their own professional ecosystems, helping to translate the project's objectives into concrete opportunities for participation, cooperation and policy dialogue.

The Ambassador model does not require a large permanent structure. Instead, it combines a central coordination function, usually performed by the Secretariat, with a distributed network of trusted representatives. This makes it particularly suitable for European projects, associations, clusters, national platforms or thematic working groups that need to reach diverse stakeholder categories across different Member States. A future facilitator could replicate the model by selecting Ambassadors with strong professional credibility, geographical reach, sectoral diversity and willingness to support community engagement over a defined period.

A key best practice from COcyber is the use of a structured, time-bound Ambassador Programme. The COcyber approach is based on several rounds of Ambassadors, each operating for a defined period of activity. This creates a manageable engagement cycle and avoids treating the Ambassador role as a vague or indefinite honorary title. A time-bound structure helps clarify expectations, maintain momentum and allow the network to evolve as the community grows. It also enables the facilitator to adjust the profile of Ambassadors over time, for example by strengthening representation from under-represented countries, defence stakeholders, SMEs, start-ups, critical infrastructure operators, academia or policy communities.

Another important best practice is the combination of visibility, engagement and intelligence-gathering functions. Ambassadors support the promotion of COcyber activities, but their role goes further than communication. They help identify relevant stakeholders, endorse activities, share targeted content, foster one-to-one engagement and support the project's position in the wider European cybersecurity arena. In practical terms, this means that Ambassadors can help increase participation in events, bring new members into the Community, identify speakers or experts, suggest topics for future activities, disseminate

project outputs and collect informal feedback from their ecosystems. This makes the Ambassador network a two-way channel: it brings COcyber messages outward, but also brings stakeholder needs, concerns and opportunities back into the governance structure.

Several lessons learned can be derived from the COcyber experience. First, the selection of Ambassadors should be based on trust, relevance and diversity, rather than visibility alone. Highly visible profiles may help dissemination, but the most valuable Ambassadors are those who can actively connect the initiative to stakeholders, open conversations and support sustained engagement. Second, the Ambassador role should be clearly described from the beginning. Ambassadors need to understand what is expected from them, including sharing information, encouraging participation, identifying collaboration opportunities and providing feedback. Third, the programme should be supported by clear communication material, regular updates and easy-to-use engagement tools. Ambassadors cannot act effectively if they lack concise messages, event information, project outputs or contact points.

For replication by other initiatives, the COcyber Ambassador model can be translated into a simple implementation pathway. First, the facilitating organisation should define the purpose of the Ambassador network and link it clearly to the objectives of the governance framework. Second, it should identify gaps in the existing community, such as countries, stakeholder categories or sectors that require stronger engagement. Third, it should select Ambassadors who can credibly address those gaps and act as bridges to relevant ecosystems. Fourth, it should provide Ambassadors with an onboarding package, including the project narrative, key messages, expected activities, communication material and points of contact. Fifth, it should maintain regular but lightweight coordination through short updates, periodic check-ins and opportunities for Ambassadors to provide feedback. Finally, it should evaluate the programme at the end of each cycle and adapt the next round accordingly.

3 Decision-making Process

The framework combines community input with efficient operational coordination. Strategic decisions are taken by the Secretariat based on Community feedback, stakeholder consultations, lessons learned from activities and alignment with European cybersecurity priorities. This approach ensures that decisions remain responsive to participant needs while preserving overall coherence and continuity. Based on the outcome of the consortium partners meetings, the Secretariat inserts their envisions events in the timeline.

The Secretariat then goes over the Activity Proposals and provides suggestions if needed. When planned, the Secretariat ensures the promotion of the event to the COcyber community. Its main goal is to consolidate inputs and ensure alignment with the overall objectives of the initiative.

In weekly meetings the Secretariat discuss updates and decide on solutions together.

Operational decisions related to event management, communication activities, stakeholder engagement and day-to-day coordination are also implemented by the Secretariat. This separation between strategic consultation and operational execution allows the framework to remain agile while still benefiting from broad stakeholder participation.

4 Stakeholder Engagement and Participation Model

Stakeholder participation is organised through a multi-tier engagement model centred on activities and the COcyber Platform. The platform functions as the primary digital collaboration environment and serves as the main entry point for community interaction. It allows an engagement with the community members and a wide participation.

Event Promotion is one of the core functions. Through the events calendar, Community members can discover and participate in workshops, consultations, seminars, roundtables and networking activities focused on dual-use cybersecurity challenges, ensuring continuous participation in the project's programme and wider cybersecurity initiatives. Centralising visibility helps avoid duplication of outreach efforts and increases access to relevant opportunities across the ecosystem. The Event Proposals mechanism allows stakeholders to suggest activities that contribute to civilian-defence cooperation objectives. This encourages bottom-up initiative generation and ensures that the programme reflects emerging needs identified by practitioners, researchers and industry actors. Proposed activities can range from technical workshops to policy roundtables or collaborative networking sessions.

Matchmaking and Networking features support the identification of potential partners, expertise providers, technology developers and collaborative opportunities. The **Partner Research** acts as a matchmaking feature that helps members showcase their organisation's

expertise, identify potential partners and connect with relevant actors through moderated introductions, using criteria such as the JRC cybersecurity taxonomy, sector and use case. These tools are particularly valuable for SMEs, start-ups and research organisations seeking connections with larger institutions, operational users or complementary projects.

The Resource Sharing space enables members to contribute reports, studies, publications, policy documents, guidance material and other resources that support collective learning. **The repository of practices** allow members to share and discover concrete examples, best practices, tools, guidelines and case studies that demonstrate how civilian and defence cybersecurity cooperation can work in practice and how lessons learned can be replicated across Europe. **The resources proposition and Knowledge Base** functions support collective learning by enabling the sharing of reports, policy documents, guidance material and other relevant resources in a single accessible space. By making knowledge easier to discover and reuse, the framework helps preserve value beyond individual events and discussions.

The **Cybersecurity Projects' Landscape, COcyber Map** and **funding sources** section further support engagement by helping members understand the wider European cybersecurity ecosystem, identify relevant EU-funded projects, explore procurement, skills and funding trends, and access R&D&I opportunities, including cybersecurity and dual-use funding programmes.

The **Policy Coach** strengthens practical engagement by offering an AI-supported, standards-aligned tool that helps organisations draft cybersecurity policies based on recognised sources such as ENISA guidance, NIS2, the NIST Cybersecurity Framework and sector-specific materials curated by the consortium. Taken together, these features make the Platform a practical engagement infrastructure that supports participation, networking, knowledge exchange, policy support, stakeholder feedback and the long-term sustainability of the COcyber Community.

Finally, **Success Stories** provide visibility for collaborative projects, innovative solutions and practical outcomes that demonstrate the benefits of cross-sector cooperation. Showcasing concrete examples helps motivate participation and illustrates how networking and knowledge exchange can lead to tangible results. Finally, Community Consultations, including surveys, feedback and consultations, ensure that stakeholder perspectives influence the evolution of activities, priorities and governance arrangements. Participation is therefore not limited to attending events, it also includes shaping the direction of the community itself.

5 Security and Information Management

Given the sensitivity of cybersecurity-related discussions, the framework promotes secure and responsible information-sharing practices. Key principles include the use of secure digital collaboration tools and compliance with applicable data protection legislation. The COcyber framework also applies Chatham House Rule when appropriate, which means that during said meetings, participants are free to use the information received but without revealing the identity and affiliation of the speaker. Those measures contribute to maintaining a trusted environment that encourages meaningful dialogue between civilian and defence stakeholders.

6 Monitoring and Evaluation

The effectiveness of the governance framework should be assessed through regular monitoring and evaluation activities. Continuous assessment ensures that the governance model remains relevant and aligned with the evolving European cybersecurity landscape. Monitoring activities should not only measure participation levels but also evaluate the quality of engagement and the overall impact of the collaboration ecosystem. Performance measurement should combine both quantitative and qualitative indicators.

A first category of indicators measures the growth and mobilisation of the COcyber Community. Monitoring the number of stakeholders involved in the organised activities therefore provides an indication of the community's attractiveness and its ability to reach relevant actors across Europe. Particular attention should be paid to the balance between stakeholder categories, paying special attention to defence organisations that will be more resistant to outreach strategies due to the sensitivity of their sector, which deals with classified information. The diversity of participation is considered equally important as the overall number of members, since the added value of the initiative derives from the interaction of different perspectives and experiences. Participation indicators also provide valuable insights into the level of engagement generated by community activities. The average number of participants attending events represents a key measure of the relevance and attractiveness of the topics addressed.

A second category of KPIs focuses on the implementation of activities. The organisation of several complementary event formats will facilitate stakeholder interest and collaboration. High-level technology roundtables facilitate strategic dialogue between senior experts and decision-makers. Cybersecurity consultations provide structured opportunities for gathering stakeholder feedback and validating project outcomes. Capacity-building activities contribute to the development of knowledge and skills among participants. Policy-oriented workshops support the formulation and refinement of recommendations addressing civilian-defence cybersecurity cooperation, while research and innovation seminars promote the dissemination of emerging technological developments and scientific expertise. Digital and cyber dialogues complement these formats by creating accessible opportunities for continuous exchange and discussion across the community.

The impact should also be ascertained through an assessment of stakeholder perceptions regarding the relevance and usefulness of project outputs. Community surveys, consultation exercises and post-event surveys provide an opportunity to capture qualitative feedback. The surveys should be short and multiple choice to facilitate the collection of answers.

An annual governance review provides an opportunity to assess whether the structure, processes and participation model remain effective. Findings from this review can inform adjustments to community engagement, coordination mechanisms, ambassador activities or decision-making practices.